

Tagungsnummer

V287

Thema

AG Bodengase

Neue Entwicklungen bei Methoden zur Messung und bei der Modellierung von Spurengasflüssen

Autoren

B. Grosz¹, R. Well¹, M. Dannenmann², R. Dechow¹, B. Kitzler³, K. Michel³, J. R. Köster¹

¹Thünen-Institut für Agrarklimaschutz, Bundesallee 50, 38116 Braunschweig, DE; ²Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research Atmospheric Environmental Research, Garmisch-Partenkirchen, DE; ³Federal Research and Training Centre for Forests, Natural Hazards and Landscape, Seckendorff-Gudent-Weg 8, 1131 Vienna, Austria

Titel

Validating soil denitrification models based on laboratory N₂ and N₂O fluxes and underlying processes: evaluation of DailyDayCent and COUP models

Abstract

Denitrification is an anaerobic key process by microbes where the NO₃⁻ is step-by-step reduced and emitted as NO, N₂O and finally N₂ gas from the soil. Accurate knowledge on denitrification dynamics is important because the N₂O is further reduced to N₂ and constitutes the main emission source of this greenhouse gas from agricultural soils. Hence, our understanding and ability to quantify soil denitrification is crucial for mitigating nitrogen fertilizer loss as well as for reducing N₂O emissions. Models can be an important tool to predict mitigation effects and help to develop climate smart mitigation strategies.

Ideally, commonly used biogeochemical models could provide adequate predictions of denitrification processes of agricultural soils but often simplified process descriptions and inadequate model parameters prevent models from simulating adequate fluxes of N₂ and N₂O on field scale. Model development and parametrization often suffers from limited availability of empirical data describing denitrification processes in agricultural soils. While in many studies N₂O emissions are used to develop and train models, detailed measurements on NO, N₂O, N₂ fluxes and concentrations and related soil conditions are necessary to develop and test adequate model algorithms.

To address this issue the coordinated research unit "Denitrification in Agricultural Soils: Integrated Control and Modelling at Various Scales (DASIM)" was initiated to more closely investigate N-fluxes caused by denitrification in response to environmental effects, soil properties and microbial communities.

Here, we present how we will use these data to evaluate common biogeochemical process models (DailyDayCent, Coup) with respect to modeled NO, N₂O and N₂ fluxes from denitrification. The models are used with different settings. The first approximation is the basic "factory" setting of the models. The next step would show the precision in the results of the modeling after adjusting the appropriate parameters from the result of the measurement values and the "factory" results. The better adjustment and the well-controlled input and output measured parameters could provide a better understanding of the probable scantiness of the tested models which will be a basis for future model improvement.